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SALTOpower

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1. INTRODUCTION

In fulfilment of SALTOpower¹ Grant Agreement on the obligations of the Consortium towards the Project Owner (PO) regarding project deliverables, the current document stands as Deliverable D5.1 - Relevant Impact Report, as described in the project Description of Action (Part A).

Given the nature of these plans, adaptations and/or changes are expected along the course of the project, befitting the objectives of assuring project dissemination, exploitation and communication. The most recent versions of documents and tools, supported by due log of changes/decisions, are made available on the project folder.

Changes to this deliverable, if needed, will be described and requested to the PO for resubmission of a later version of this document.

2. SALTOPOWER WIDENING IMPACTS

Following the project objectives of raising UEvora Widening profile:

“Engaging two top-class leading partners around a scientific strategy for stepping up and stimulating scientific excellence and innovation capacity on the use of Molten Salt technologies as a Key Clean Energy Transition solution, SALTOpower aims at enhanced networking with the Coordinator Widening partner, raising its research profile through the exploitation of their staff and infrastructural synergies in the establishment of the Reference European Facility in Molten Salt Research for Energy applications.”,

upon implementation of coordination and support measures aiming at the achievement, by the Widening institution (UEvora) of the 4CWC: Excellence Research, Attractive Careers, Aligned Strategy and Relevant Impact, the vision of SALTOpower “Widening impacts” (WI’s) comprises:

- **WI.1:** EMSP @ UEvora delivers world-class research results in the field of Molten Salt technologies for energy applications;
- **WI.2:** UEvora staff and structure present improved technical and administrative skills, enabling a more efficient research management encompassing state-of-the-art procedures adapted to its context;
- **WI.3:** UEvora is able to attract and retain Young Researchers at both the national and international levels;
- **WI.4:** UEvora integrates the most important international research fora and is acknowledged as an important partner by Industry;
- **WI.5:** UEvora research reaches 4Helix actors, is protected, accessible and exploited.

2.1. EMSP @ UEvora delivers world-class research

The Renewable Energies Chair research group at the University of Évora (UEvora-CER) is dedicated to advancing world-class scientific research in the specialized area of Molten Salt (MS) technologies for energy applications (WI.1). This commitment is reflected in the establishment of a devoted research team within the UEvora-CER that actively pursues cutting-edge studies to push the State of the Art (SoA) into this emerging field. The group’s work is centered on the development and optimization of MS technologies, with a particular focus on their applications in energy storage systems and renewable gas production, two critical pillars for the global energy transition. By integrating applied research with innovative technological development, UEvora-CER fosters a research environment aimed to scientific breakthroughs that address critical energy challenges. The team’s research activities are structured around the Joint Research Activity (JRA), which facilitates the coordinated engagement of Senior Researchers (SR), Young Researchers (YR), and Candidate Young Researchers (CYR), thus fostering the

¹ Project: 101079303 — SALTOpower — HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03

establishment of a talent pool in the field of research. This approach not only strengthens research capacity but also promotes the development of early-career scientists through training and mentoring aligned with the project's objectives. Furthermore, UEvora's Research Infrastructure (RI) is continuously upgraded and expanded to support these advanced investigations, ensuring that the institution remains at the forefront of MS technology innovation. Through this integrated research strategy, Evora Molten Salt Platform (EMSP) at UEvora contributes significantly to scientific excellence while positioning itself as a key player in both national and international research networks, driving forward the sustainable energy agenda with impactful outcomes.

The Joint Research Activity (JRA) currently involves the participation of 1 Senior Researcher (SR), 4 Young Researchers (YRs), and 3 Candidate Young Researchers (CYRs). Dedicated teams, composed of YR and CYR personnel, have been assigned to and have successfully concluded tasks T2.1 and T2.2, concerning MS-driven Thermo-Electrochemical H₂/syngas production and MS-based Carnot Battery systems, respectively. Furthermore, a comprehensive concept for a SoA and beyond SoA has been developed and is formally documented in Deliverable 2.1 (D2.1). This beyond SoA concept is illustrated in Figure 1.

The upgrade of the Widening RI represents a critical undertaking with the objective of expanding capabilities in MS energy storage and renewable gas production. This initiative, which is a component of Deliverable 2.2, is documented in a comprehensive R&D report that specifies the materials list and technical requirements for the upgrade at the EMSP.

The design of the RI upgrade is guided by two principal factors: the integration requirements established by UEvora and the technical assessment derived from Tasks 2.1 and 2.2, which serves to define the "beyond SoA test bed". This strategic enhancement bases the development of the ensuing project proposals, concurring to raise UEvora research profile by means of cutting-edge research (SALTOpower Objective 1) through the upgrade of the Widening RI (KPI 1.2) and the participation in more R&D project proposals (KPI 1.3), enabling an upgraded scope of research and services and the development of new avenues of research.

The Widening RI focuses on three distinct molten salt loops: the HPS2-Loop, the NEWSOL loop, and the Schott loop. Detailed specifications and material lists have been prepared for each to guide the selection process (see Figure 2).

Table 1 details the significant progress achieved toward Widening Impact 1 (WI.1), which is focused on enabling the Molten Salt Platform (EMSP) at the University of Évora (UEvora) to deliver world-class research in Molten Salt (MS) technologies for energy applications.

The summary highlights both the successful mobilization of human resources and the strategic advancement of the research infrastructure (RI). Key status indicators confirm that UEvora has established a devoted research team, with 1 Senior Researcher (SR), 4 Young Researchers (YR), and 3 Candidate Young Researchers (CYR) actively engaged in the Joint Research Activity (JRA) and has successfully defined specialized teams to tackle specific technical tasks (T2.1 and T2.2). Furthermore, initial RI upgrade activities are well underway, including the definition of the necessary intervention, materials lists, and engineering work, following the successful development of the State-of-the-Art (SoA) and beyond-SoA concepts (D2.1). These actions lay a solid foundation for accelerating applied research in MS energy storage and renewable gas production.

Figure 1. A conceptual diagram of MS-TES/-Carnot Batteries as inter-grid integrator solutions to produce heat, electricity and fuels using electricity and heat stored in TES.

HPS2-Salt cycle loop-possible in & outlet

Possible inlets	1,2,3
Maximum temperature	Up to 560°C
Minimum measured mass flow	4kg/s
Maximum measured flow rate	11.15kg/s (for inlet 1 and 2)
Composition of MS - %	60%NaNO3 40%KNO3
Possible outlets	4,5
Maximum temperature	300°C
Minimum level of CT&HT	600mm
Maximum level of CT&HT	4400mm

HPS2-W/S cycle possible in & outlet

Possible inlet/outlet	1, 2
Maximum temperature	530°C
Maximum mass flow	0.7kg/s
Pressure	140bar
Cooling capacity (3,4)	<500kWt

NEWSOL+SCHOTT LOOP-possible in and outlets

Parameters	1, 2, 3, 4
Maximum temperature	500°C
Minimum temperature	200°C
Nominal mass flow	5kg/s
Electrical power	90kWt
Cooling capacity	500kWt
Composition of MS - %	42% CaNO3, 43%KNO3, 15%NaNO3

Figure 2. An excerpt from the technical details and materials list for Widening RI upgrades.

Table 1. Summary of Progress towards Widening Impact 1 (WI.1): Delivering World-Class Research in Molten Salt Technologies.

WI.1: EMSP @ UEvora delivers world-class research results in the field of Molten Salt technologies for energy applications		
Description	Pathway	Status
- UEvora-CER has a devoted research team developing cutting-edge research on Molten Salt technologies	- Engagement of UEvora SR (Senior), YR (Young) and CYR (Candidate Young Researcher) in the JRA	- 1 UEVORA SR, 4 YR and 3 CYR are engaged in the JRA;

		- 2 YR+CYR teams have been defined to tackle T2.1 and T2.2 respectively
- UEvora RI enables the development of applied research aiming the further development of MS technologies and their further applications in energy storage and link to renewable gases	- Development of the JRA (WP2) including a Widening RI upgrade to ensuing activities in MS energy storage and renewable gas production	- A SoA and beyond SoA concept have been developed (D2.1); RI upgrade activities are undergoing (RI intervention defined; materials list and engineering undergoing)

2.2. UEvora staff and structure present improved technical and administrative skills

UEvora is strengthening the technical and administrative capacities of its staff and organizational structures to ensure more efficient and effective research management tailored to its specific context (WI.2). This improvement is achieved through the enhancement of project management procedures that integrate existing general management tools, such as financial execution tracking and timesheet registries, into comprehensive project execution control processes, including technical monitoring and Gantt chart oversight. A key aspect of this pathway is the integration of public procurement-based purchasing and hiring procedures into an internal UEvora platform, which facilitates continuous monitoring of administrative workflows, automatic process alerts, and estimated completion timelines. The engagement of the UEvora Science and Cooperation Service (SCC) in project coordination activities ensures dedicated oversight and streamlined management. Additionally, targeted project management workshops provided essential training to staff, fostering a shared understanding of best practices.

Particularly, in an effort to enhance operational efficiency and strategic output, a new management tool has been successfully adapted and implemented (OpenProject tool, Figure 3). This has been complemented by the development and application of new purchasing procedures to ensure a more streamlined and transparent process.

Figure 3. SALTOpower project in OpenProject platform.

The commitment to project excellence is demonstrated through the application of Quality and Risk Management tools, which have been applied in full alignment with the PM² methodology. PM² methodology artifacts and implementation in the SALTOpower project are shown in Figure 4 and in Figure 5, respectively. All Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) activities are now overseen by a dedicated communication manager, ensuring effective outreach and impact dissemination.

Figure 4. PM² Artifacts in SALTOpower project for Communication Management Plan and Deliverables Acceptance Plan.

According to the SheFigures 2024 report and despite notable progress, significant efforts are still required to achieve full Gender Equality (GE) across the European Union, including in Germany, Italy, and Portugal, countries presented in the SALTOpower consortium. In response, SALTOpower implemented a series of targeted activities aimed at promoting GE, including initiatives to improve work-life balance, leadership training programmes, and awareness-raising seminars. Survey results revealed a limited awareness of existing institutional GE measures, suggesting the need for enhanced communication and more effective implementation. The project also addressed persistent gender imbalances in leadership roles, structural barriers to women's career advancement, and the integration of the gender dimension in research and teaching. Furthermore, measures to combat gender-based violence and sexual harassment were identified as essential, particularly in improving reporting procedures and institutional responses. Overall, the activities carried out under the SALTOpower project fostered inclusive dialogue, strengthened institutional awareness, and led to concrete proposals for advancing gender equality within participating organizations.

Furthermore, a series of strategic initiatives have been launched to foster an inclusive environment. These include the implementation of gender equality initiatives, the organization of informative seminars, and the distribution of questionnaires. The institution has also successfully organized several regional forums, national and international Energy Symposium events and has invested in professional development through the provision of specialized leadership training (Figure 3). Through these combined measures, UEvora significantly upgrades its technical and administrative capabilities, ensuring alignment with state-of-the-art procedures and increasing overall institutional efficiency.

*This checklist should be reviewed and customized (if needed), when planning quality. The main purpose of the Quality Review Checklist is to support the Project Quality Reviewers when verifying if key project activities were performed as

Project Quality Review	
Organisation / Department:	University of Evora / Renewable Energies Chair
Project Name:	SALTOpower
Project Owner:	European Commission
Business Manager:	Benjamin Dobbelaere
Solution Provider:	University of Evora
Project Manager:	Pedro Horta
Project Quality Reviewer:	UEVORA - SCC
Review Date:	15.02.2023
Overall Score:	96%
Overall Project Quality Assessment	0.96

Area	% of Quality Compliance	Score	Included?
Scope	96%	96%	Yes
Schedule	96%	96%	Yes
Cost	100%	100%	Yes
Quality	92%	92%	Yes
Risk	100%	100%	Yes
Issues & Decisions	93%	93%	Yes
Communication	88%	88%	Yes
Project Organisation	93%	93%	Yes
Outsourcing	100%	100%	Yes
Client Satisfaction	100%	100%	Yes

SALTOPOWER_LOGS.28-05-2025.v1.0														
Ficheiro Editar Ver Inserir Formatar Dados Ferramentas Ajuda														
Menu														
100%														
Calibri														
11														
B														
U														
A														
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Y														
X														
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F														
E														
D														
C														
B														
A														
Risk Identification and Description														
ID	Category	Title	Description	Related Task	Status	Identified By	Identification Date	Likelihood (L)	Impact (I)	Risk Level (L*I)	Risk Owner	Escalation	SUITABLE RESPONSE	Risk Response Strategy
RI.001	People & Organisation	Loss of key personnel	Loss of key personnel in the project management structure.	T1.1: Project Management	Approved	Consortium	2022-01-18	3	3	9	PM	Y	Reduce	Reduce
RI.002	People & Organisation	Faulty coordination.	Lack of coordination between partners.	T1.1: Project Management	Closed	Consortium	2022-01-18	2	3	6	PSC	Y	Reduce	Reduce
RI.003	External or Legal	Travel restrictions	Covid-19 pandemic not allowing for travelling.	T1.1: Project Management	Closed	Consortium	2022-01-18	3	2	6	PM	Y	Reduce	Reduce
RI.004	Infrastructure	RI upgrade not viable.	RI upgrade implementation on EMSF HPS2-loop technically not possible.	T2.3: Widening upgrade	Closed	Consortium	2022-01-18	2	3	6	PCT (WP2)	Y	Reduce	Reduce
RI.005	External or Legal	Competitiveness	Technical-economic assessment results stand for lack of competitiveness of the foreseen technological solution.	T2.2: MS based Carnot Battery systems	Approved	Consortium	2022-01-18	3	3	9	PCT (WP2)	Y	Reduce	Reduce
RI.006	Infrastructure	Infrastructure priorities	Due to parallel activities in the infrastructure setting different "top access" priorities, required space for the ensuing installation of prototypes ceases to exist at the foreseen location.	T2.3: Widening upgrade	Closed	Consortium	2022-01-18	3	3	9	PCT (WP2)	Y	Reduce	Reduce
RI.007	Infrastructure	Syngas post-process	Technical constraints (e.g. available space, security) to the installation of syngas post-processing hardware (H2 separation and cleaning/compressing units, methanation and storage units) does not allow full fledged renewable gas/fuel production in ensuing projects.	T4.4: Ensuing Joint Projects	Approved	Consortium	2022-01-18	3	3	9	PCT (WP2)	Y	Reduce	Reduce
RI.008	Infrastructure	Infrastructure access	Access to some assets of the facility is hampered by previous "asset ownership" agreements and/or "closed" software and/or communication protocols (e.g. solar field, thermal storage, steam generator)	T2.4: Distributed Facility	Closed	Consortium	2022-01-18	3	3	9	PCT (WP2)	Y	Reduce	Reduce
RI.009	External or Legal	FT School attendance	Fast-Track Schools have no registered attendants.	T3.1: Training	Closed	Consortium	2022-01-18	2	4	8	PCT (WP3)	Y	Reduce	Reduce
RI.010	Adhesion	CVR engagement	A 2nd CVR is not identified by MID.	T3.2: Tutoring	Invalido		2022-01-18	3	4	12	PM	Y	Reduce	Reduce
RI.011	Adhesion	Living Amenities	Living Amenities pass has no subscriptions	T3.3: Living			2022-01-18	3	2	6	PCT (WP3)	Y	Reduce	Reduce
RI.012	Adhesion	RSFora	Lack of interest in participation in RSFora	T4.1: Policy alignment	Closed	Consortium	2022-01-18	2	3	6	PCT (WP4)	Y	Reduce	Reduce

Figure 5. PM² methodology implemented in SALTOpower project for Quality review checklist and Risk Review.

Figure 6. Regional Specialization Fora held by UEvora.

Table 2 summarizes the substantial progress achieved toward Widening Impact 2 (WI.2), which targets the enhancement of UEvora’s technical and administrative skills and structures to ensure more efficient research management. This impact is critical for adapting state-of-the-art procedures to the university's specific context.

Key status indicators confirm that UEvora has successfully focused on integrating advanced management tools. The PM2 methodology was presented during the Kick-off Meeting (KoM) and a complete PM2-based project management framework (D1.1) has since been

implemented, supported by a dedicated collaborator from the Technical and Administrative Staff (TADM) working directly on management and Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) activities. Furthermore, to streamline administrative workflows, UEvora has focused on procurement: an experimental purchasing platform is currently operational within the research group, and one of its core functionalities has already been successfully transferred to the centralized institutional system. These steps mark a significant move toward institutionalizing efficient and modern research management practices.

Table 2. Summary of Progress towards Widening Impact 2 (WI.2): Enhancing Research Management Skills and Efficiency.

WI.2: UEvora staff and structure present improved technical and administrative skills enabling a more efficient research management encompassing state-of-the-art procedures adapted to its context		
Description	Pathway	Status
- UEvora project management procedures are enhanced and integrate already existing general management tools (financial execution, timesheet registry) into project execution control procedures (technical execution, Gantt monitoring)	- UEvora-SCC are engaged in Project Coordination activities - Dedicated Project Management procedures workshop (by the time of KOM)	- UEvora-SCC services have a detached TADM collaborator working in the project management and DEC activities - PM2 methodology has been presented along KoM and a PM2 based project management framework has been implemented (D1.1)
- Public procurement-based purchasing and hiring procedures are integrated into internal UEvora platform enabling monitoring of administrative process, process alerts and estimated conclusion	- Development of internal purchasing platform	- An experimental purchasing platform has been developed and is under use in the research group ; one functionality has been passed to the centralized system

2.3. UEvora is able to attract and retain Young Researchers

UEvora emphasizes its successful ability to attract and retain Young Researchers (YR) at both the national and international levels, fostering a dynamic research community within the SALTOpower framework (WI.3). Young Researchers at UEvora are nurtured to become leading experts in their respective fields, often taking on leadership roles by heading dedicated research teams focused on SALTOpower topics. Candidate Young Researchers (CYR) nearing the completion of their PhD studies are fully integrated into UEvora’s research environment with clear pathways to transition into YR positions, while the institution also attracts international CYRs whose doctoral research aligns closely with the Joint Research Activity (JRA). Engagement in the JRA is further supported through access to targeted training and mentoring programs offered in collaboration with TOP partners and Research Infrastructures (RI), including participation in SALTOpower Fast-Track Schools that provide critical know-how and foster international networking. Career development is actively supported, with opportunities such as preparing for ERC proposals to advance professional growth. Additionally, the attractiveness of living in Évora, combined with dedicated Living Amenities and mentoring initiatives, creates a supportive environment that encourages retention and personal development. These combined efforts ensure a dynamic and sustainable flow of talented researchers who contribute significantly to UEvora’s research excellence.

UEvora’s Young Researcher (YR) has established themselves as a leading researcher in the SALTOpower field, and they are fully engaged in the development of the Joint Research Activity (JRA). This researcher leads a devoted team in these topics and is provided with access to training and mentoring from TOP partners and TOP RIs. Concurrently, the CYRs at UEvora are

approaching the completion of their PhD research. The objective is for these individuals to become YRs and be integrated into the dedicated UEvora team. Their PhD theses are closely aligned with the SALTOpower JRA, and they benefit from training and tutoring provided by TOP partners and a TOP RIs. The SALTOpower Fast-Track Schools serve a critical function by delivering specialized know-how and engaging an international audience of both YRs and CYRs.

In the framework of the SALTOpower project, two key initiatives have been implemented to support the professional growth of researchers: Tutoring and Mentoring. The tutoring program is designed to support Candidate Young Researchers (CYRs) in the development of their PhD theses, facilitating a total of 5.6 weeks of mobility for CYRs from UEvora to TOP partners, ENEA and DLR. The mentoring initiative, conversely, is aimed at the career development of Young Researchers (YRs) who are engaged in the project, with the specific goal of preparing them for future leadership roles in the SALTOpower field. A satisfaction survey conducted in November 2024, with responses from six CYRs and YRs, indicated high levels of satisfaction with the project. The team satisfaction was rated at an average of 5.00 out of 5, while the general satisfaction with SALTOpower received an average rating of 4.33. Additionally, to further support career progression towards leadership positions, a dedicated leadership training program is scheduled for the UEvora team, including both YRs and CYRs, in May 2025 and targeted in September 2025.

In alignment with SALTOpower's objective to foster the career advancement of Young Researchers (YRs), targeted support has been provided for the preparation and submission of proposals to the ERC Starting Grant scheme, one of the most competitive and prestigious funding instruments in the European research landscape, aimed at researchers with 2 to 7 years of postdoctoral experience. As a result of a systematic eligibility assessment conducted across the Consortium, four YRs were identified as eligible candidates for application.

Surpassing the project's initial target of submitting two ERC Starting Grant proposals, one application (EFESTO), submitted by Francesco Aldo Rovense (ENEA), was officially submitted to the 2024 call. The project focused on improving the stability of nanoparticle-enhanced phase change materials (NEPCM) for thermal energy storage through the application of external magnetic fields. Although the proposal was not selected to proceed to the second evaluation stage, it provided valuable experience in ERC proposal development.

In parallel, three additional ERC Starting Grant proposals have been prepared and submitted to the ERC-2026-StG call. These include:

- MS-DINAMIC by Radia Ait El Cadi (UEvora), focusing on the design and experimental validation of an upgraded molten salt infrastructure for Carnot battery research and technology transfer;
- ZEOCAT-H₂ by Asma Nouira (UEvora), proposing an innovative, circular hydrogen production process using sewage sludge as both feedstock and catalytic material in a solar-assisted gasification system;
- NEXFUEL by Imen Amri (UEvora), aiming to develop a nanoemulsion-based thermochemical platform for the conversion of CO₂ into renewable drop-in fuels, integrating molten salt thermal storage and solar-driven redox cycles.

These proposals reflect a high level of scientific ambition and strategic alignment with SALTOpower's thematic areas, including thermal energy storage, advanced materials, and renewable fuels. The mentoring and proposal development activities within Task 3.2, as well as the support from national programs such as ERC-PT, have played a crucial role in enabling these applications. This engagement with the ERC framework represents a significant step toward positioning SALTOpower's Young Researchers as future leaders in the European research ecosystem.

The PhD programs developed within the framework of the Joint Research Activity (JRA) are centered on the application of Molten Salts (MS) for Carnot batteries and thermochemical

hydrogen production. Three specific PhD programs have been delineated, two of which are currently underway:

- The "Technical and Economic Feasibility of Green Hydrogen Production from Agricultural Waste" program, aligned with JRA Task T2.1, focuses on the production of green hydrogen from agricultural waste, such as olive mill wastewater, through thermochemical processes integrated with solar energy.
- The "Competitiveness of Carnot Batteries in Power Generation and Industrial Applications" program, linked to JRA Task T2.2, analyzes the competitiveness and various applications of Carnot batteries in comparison to other energy storage solutions.
- The "Integration of Carnot Batteries into the Energy System" thesis, also correlated with JRA Task T2.2, aims to evaluate the optimal integration of Carnot batteries to enhance grid stability and the efficiency of renewable energy source integration.

CYR (Career Young Researchers) and YR (Young Researchers) were among the main target groups of the Fast-Track Schools (FTS), which were designed as progressive training sessions throughout the SALTOpower project. The FTS aimed to provide CYR and YR, as well as industry engineers and technicians, with advanced knowledge and hands-on experience in key areas of molten salt technology. The training evolved over three editions, covering:

- Fundamentals and state-of-the-art in molten salt research (Rome, May 2023),
- Experimental procedures and practical implementation (Cologne, July 2024),
- Technology benchmarking and exploitation strategies (Évora, November 2024).

These schools (Figure 4) helped to develop technical skills and project-relevant expertise for CYRs and YRs, enhancing their professional growth and preparing them to contribute actively to the project's goals.

Figure 7. The three editions of the FTS.

The original concept for a "Living Amenities Pass" was conceived to assist new researchers with integration into the local community. However, its implementation faced significant legal and administrative obstacles, particularly concerning financial management and public procurement regulations. As a result, the project consortium adopted a revised approach, pivoting from the pass to a new, two-part solution. The first component is an expanded "Living in Alentejo" section on the project website (Figure 5), which provides newcomers with a comprehensive set of resources, including a map of key points of interest, a calendar of local events, and useful contacts. The second and more significant component is the "Mentoring Initiative" (Figure 6). This program pairs new researchers, referred to as "mentees," with volunteer "mentors" from the UEvora's research and technical staff. The mentors' role is to provide practical assistance with non-work-related matters, such as finding accommodation and navigating administrative processes, thereby facilitating the mentees' successful integration into the city and region.

Figure 8. "Living in Alentejo" on the SALTOpower website.

Figure 9. "Mentoring Program" on the SALTOpower website.

Table 3 indicates the key status achieved toward Widening Impact 3 (WI.3), which focuses on UEvora's ability to attract and retain Young Researchers (YR) at both the national and international levels. This impact is central to building a sustainable, high-quality research team.

The data confirms significant success in engaging and developing talent. All 4 YRs are fully engaged in the Joint Research Activity (JRA) across tasks T2.1 and T2.2, with tangible career development pathways established: all 4 YRs defined mentoring arrangements with top partners, all have completed mobility periods in two TOP Research Infrastructures (RI), and the institution has identified 4 eligible YRs to pursue competitive ERC proposal calls. Similarly, Candidate Young Researchers (CYRs) are being successfully integrated: all 3 CYRs are developing PhD theses aligned with the JRA topics and have attended the Fast-Track School. Finally, UEvora has enhanced its external appeal by implementing the Mentoring Program as alternative to

Living Amenities, making the location more attractive, serviceable and enjoyable to both national and international researchers.

Table 3. Summary of Progress towards Widening Impact 3 (WI.3): Attraction and Retention of Young Researchers.

WI.3: UEvora is able to attract and retain Young Researchers at both national and international level		
Description	Pathway	Status
- UEvora YR becomes a leading researcher in SALTOpower research field leading a devoted team in these topics	- YR fully engaged in the development of the JRA - YR has access to Training and Mentoring activities with TOP partners and TOP RI - YR career development through an ERC proposal	- 4 YR engaged in the development of the JRA, along T2.1 (3) and T2.2 (1) topics, respectively - 2 YR have attended FTSchool and 1 provided contents ; 4 YR had mobility in 2 TOP RI; 4 YR have defined mentoring by TOP partners - ERC proposal calls identified and 4 eligible YR identified
- UEvora CYR is close to the completion of the PhD research and aims at becoming a YR integrated in UEvora devoted team - UEvora is able to attract an international CYR developing a PhD integrated and aligned with SALTOpower JRA	- CYRs develop PhD thesis aligned with (a) SALTOpower JRA and have access to Training and Tutoring with TOP partners and TOP RI (b) - SALTOpower Fast-Track Schools deliver know-how and engage an international audience of YR and CYR	- 3 CYR are developing PhD thesis aligned with JRA in T2.1 and T2.2 topic, respectively; 3 CYR have attended FTSchool
- Living in Évora is attractive to national and international YR and CYR	- Living Amenities facility	- Living Amenities contents implemented in SALTOpower website ; Alternative to pass implemented.

2.4. UEvora integrates the most important international research fora and is acknowledged as an important partner by Industry

UEvora's efforts have led to its active integration into key international research forums and its recognition as a valuable partner by industry stakeholders (WI.4). The university has enhanced its profile through updated and expanded participation in prominent organizations such as the European Energy Research Alliance's Joint Programme on Concentrated Solar Power (EERA JP-CSP), demonstrating its commitment to contributing cutting-edge research and innovation. In pursuit of greater international engagement, UEvora has formally applied for Portuguese representation in SolarPACES, a major global platform for solar thermal research, supported by strategic lobbying efforts with the Portuguese Ministry of Science and Technology. UEvora's collaboration with industry is strengthened through joint research activities conducted within the Widening RI, facilitating direct knowledge transfer and co-development of innovative solutions. Furthermore, the university provides specialized R&D services to industrial partners under formal service contracts, enhancing practical application and technology deployment. This multifaceted engagement is supported by a dedicated proposal facility aimed at securing funding to sustain and expand these collaborative efforts. Collectively, these initiatives position UEvora as a key player at the intersection of research excellence and industry relevance on both national and international stages.

UEvora has strengthened its institutional presence in the European solar research landscape by presenting an updated and upgraded profile of participation in the EERA Joint Programme on Concentrated Solar Power (JP-CSP). In parallel, UEvora has submitted an application to represent Portugal in the international SolarPACES initiative, reinforcing its role in global CSP collaboration. At the national level, UEvora has actively engaged industrial partners in joint research activities within the Widening Research Infrastructure – whose formal integration as a full member in ERIC EU-SOLARIS has also been presented - fostering innovation through collaborative development. Additionally, UEvora provides specialized R&D services to an industrial partner under a formal service contract, further consolidating its position as a key research and technology provider in the solar energy sector.

Within the scope of the SALTOpower project, several R&D and service proposals have been developed and submitted under the framework of the Proposals Facility (T4.4). These proposals focus on key technological areas such as molten salt-based Carnot batteries and thermo-/electrochemical hydrogen and syngas production. The proposals target a varied range of funding sources, including European, regional, and (prospectively) national programs. Notable European proposals include *HESTIA*, coordinated by Fraunhofer ISE and involving UEvora in experimental validation activities. At the regional level, the *SALBIOFUEL* project was submitted by UEvora to explore the integration of molten salt thermal systems with biomass thermochemical reactors, addressing synthetic fuel production from agroforestry waste. In parallel, UEvora has submitted multiple service proposals to support industrial and research stakeholders through its EMSP infrastructure. These include experimental campaigns for the MSOPERA, ADVIAMOS, and SPOT projects, as well as infrastructure upgrades, such as a 6MVA substation installation for the LHEXMS project. These initiatives demonstrate UEvora's strategic commitment to advancing MS technology through both research and service-oriented collaboration with academia and industry.

The proposal *SCOREFUEL*, submitted in February 2025 (Call: HORIZON-CL5-2024-D3-02), aims to develop and demonstrate a high-efficiency, cost-effective, and environmentally sustainable CO₂ conversion technology, powered by renewable energy and integrated with molten salt thermal storage systems. The project focuses on converting captured industrial CO₂, both directly and via microalgae-based slurry, into advanced synthetic fuels. These fuels are tailored for use in hard-to-abate sectors such as aerospace, aviation, and maritime transport, offering a promising pathway toward the decarbonization of industries with limited alternatives for emissions reduction. The proposal *SALTIS*, submitted in September 2025 (Call: HORIZON-INFRA-2025-01), aims to position molten salt technologies at the forefront of Europe's long-duration energy storage solutions, addressing the urgent need for flexible, scalable, and CRM-free alternatives to Li-ion batteries. *SALTIS* focuses on strengthening and coordinating the EU-SOLARIS network of research infrastructures. The project will support the operational deployment of molten salts as long-duration thermal energy storage and heat transfer media, leveraging their high efficiency, long lifetime, sector-coupling capabilities, and reliance on widely available European materials. By advancing research and innovation across the entire molten salt value chain, from salt mixtures to components like pumps, valves, and heat exchangers, the *SALTIS* project aims to contribute to the EU's energy transition strategy. This effort will strengthen EU-SOLARIS as a reference research infrastructure for energy storage, filling a critical gap in the ERIC landscape.

The SALTOpower Consortium is currently preparing two proposals: *SASYFUEL* (Call: HORIZON-EIC-2025-PATHFINDERCHALLENGES-01) and *CHLORSTEP* (Call: HORIZON-CL5-2026-02-D3-05).

Table 4 provides a concise overview of the progress attained under Widening Impact 4 (WI.4), which aims to secure UEvora's integration into the most important international research fora and establish its recognition as a key partner by industry stakeholders.

The status confirms successful efforts to strengthen both strategic networking and industrial engagement. UEvora has actively lobbied the Portuguese Science and Technology Ministry to support its engagement with SolarPACES, with formal participation for Portugal now under discussion. Furthermore, UEvora has successfully enhanced its profile within the EERA Joint Programme-CSP by extending its participation to the crucial SP5 Solar Thermochemical Production of Fuels area. Concurrently, UEvora has substantially improved its outreach to industrial partners by developing and utilizing a PM2-based proposal writing support tool. This facility has yielded tangible results, including the submission of 7 EU proposals, 3 regional proposals, and 5 service proposals, demonstrating UEvora's commitment to both collaborative research and providing R&D services to industry.

Table 4. Summary of Progress towards Widening Impact 4 (WI.4): International Networking and Industrial Partnership.

WI.4: UEvora integrates the most important international research fora and is acknowledged as an important partner by Industry		
Description	Pathway	Status
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UEvora presents an updated and upgraded profile of participation in EERA JP-CSP - UEvora applies for a Portuguese representation in SolarPACES 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UEvora participation extended to SP5 Solar Thermochemical Production of Fuels - Lobbying with the Portuguese Science and Technology Ministry to support UEvora engagement in SolarPACES 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Formal participation of Portugal in SolarPACES has been formally requested and is under national ministerial approval - Full membership of Portugal in ERIC EU-SOLARIS has been formally requested and is under national ministerial approval
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UEvora engages Industrial partners in joint research activities in the Widening RI - UEvora provides R&D services to Industrial partner under a service contract 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Proposal Facility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A PM2 based proposal writing support tool has been developed and is under use; 7 EU proposals, 3 Regional proposal and 5 service proposals have been submitted

2.5. UEvora research reaches 4Helix actors

UEvora ensures the broad dissemination, protection, accessibility, and exploitation of its research within the 4Helix innovation model, which encompasses academia, industry, policymakers, and civil society (WI.5). Research outputs from UEvora's Research Infrastructure (RI) and Joint Research Activity (JRA) are consistently presented in peer-reviewed journals and major scientific conferences, such as SolarPACES and ISES, ensuring visibility and validation within the global scientific community. The impact of SALTOpower research is explicitly aligned with the ongoing energy transition and correlates strongly with national and regional industrial strategies and specialization agendas, fostering clear relevance to academic, policy, and industrial stakeholders alike. To safeguard innovations and maximize their commercial potential, UEvora has developed a robust Intellectual Property (IP) protection framework and a comprehensive Commercial Exploitation Plan, formalized through a "Spin-off Blueprint" that guides the creation of new companies. Additionally, UEvora researchers and staff maintain close integration with local actors, facilitating contextualized knowledge transfer and regional development. This comprehensive approach is further supported by dedicated events such as the SALTOpower Energy Transition Symposium and Regional Specialization Forum, alongside the provision of Living Amenities, which collectively strengthen community engagement and ensure research output effectively contributes to sustainable innovation ecosystems.

One of the main objectives of the SALTOpower project's dissemination strategy was to ensure the publication of scientific results in peer-reviewed, open-access journals whenever possible.

By the end of the project, eight peer-reviewed articles had been submitted, with three already published and five pending publications. Additionally, over 15 other scientific contributions were produced within the scope of SALTOpower, although they do not formally acknowledge the project. All eligible publications, along with their associated datasets and metadata, were deposited in Zenodo, in alignment with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data principles. Zenodo was chosen over alternative repositories such as OpenAIRE for its seamless functionality, data hosting flexibility, and strong commitment to long-term preservation, backed by CERN and the European OpenAIRE programme. A complete list of publications, including DOIs and repository links, is available in deliverable D5.2 Final Report on DEC.

In support of SALTOpower's objective to strengthen the networking of UEvora within scientific and industrial forums, a series of strategic activities were conducted, including the Regional Specialization Forums, the Energy Strategy Symposium, and the Energy Transition Symposium. These events were designed to maximize SALTOpower's impact across the 4Helix framework, encompassing academia, policymakers, industry, and civil society, at regional, national, and international levels. The Regional Specialization Forums, focusing on the Alentejo region, revealed that while some industrial expertise exists in installation and operation and maintenance services, primarily derived from the petrochemical sector in Sines, no significant manufacturing capabilities were identified. This observation reflects the predominantly agricultural economic profile of the region. Despite positive engagement and a growing number of participants, these findings highlighted the necessity of adopting a nationwide approach to foster an ecosystem capable of supporting Molten Salt value chains. The national-level Energy Strategy Symposium attracted a diverse group of stakeholders and addressed SALTOpower's technological solutions, their alignment with the decarbonization targets set by the National Energy and Climate Plan and the European 2050 Energy Roadmap, and Portugal's industrial capacities. Notably, it was observed that regional coverage of SALTOpower-related value chains is limited, particularly in manufacturing, whereas national coverage is considerably higher, suggesting that industrial engagement would benefit from broader partnerships extending beyond the Alentejo region to more industrialized areas in northern Portugal. Participant feedback indicated substantial interest in the presented technologies, particularly as complementary solutions for energy storage diversification. The international Energy Transition Symposium engaged stakeholders from consortium countries in a focused dialogue on technology perception, market regulation, demonstration initiatives, industrial leadership, and impact promotion. Dominated by industry representatives, the symposium facilitated the identification of concrete measures aimed at increasing dissemination, simplifying regulatory frameworks, enhancing incentive mechanisms, and strengthening the connection between research infrastructure and market uptake. The potential establishment of a European Association on Molten Salt technologies was also proposed to coordinate these efforts effectively. Collectively, these activities achieved significant engagement across targeted audiences and provided a solid foundation for continued collaborative actions to advance SALTOpower's strategic objectives.

Figure 10. Energy Strategy Symposium and Energy Transition Symposium events.

In the framework of the SALTOpower project a Spin-Off Facility has been developed, dedicated to both YRs and CYRs (Figure 8). This initiative provided structured guidance on the creation of spin-off companies, including legal, financial, and fiscal aspects, as well as intellectual property protection strategies. Developed in collaboration with the Innovation and Entrepreneurship Office of the University of Évora (DIC2E), the facility included seminars and practical materials covering the full innovation cycle—from ideation and validation to market entry and investor engagement. An "Innovation Assets Matrix" was also introduced to map and assess existing support resources within the Widening institution and partner organizations, with the aim of identifying gaps and fostering inter-consortium collaboration. A business model study is underway to explore the potential of operating the upgraded research facility (developed under WP2) as an independent service provider, serving as a practical blueprint for spin-off creation. Selected materials from the Spin-Off Facility will be made publicly available via the project’s Zenodo repository.

Figure 11. Exemplary contents of Spin-Off facility materials.

The original "Living Amenities Pass" aimed to help new researchers integrate locally but faced legal and administrative challenges. The project shifted to a two-part solution: an expanded "Living in Alentejo" website section offering key local resources, and a "Mentoring Initiative" pairing new researchers with University of Évora staff volunteers who assist with practical, non-work-related matters to ease their integration, as indicated in the section 2.3.

The table below provides a concise summary of the progress achieved under Widening Impact 5 (WI.5), which is designed to ensure UEvora’s research is protected, accessible, and effectively exploited across the 4Helix actors (Academia, Industry, Government, and Civil society).

The status confirms successful execution across all dissemination and exploitation fronts. UEvora’s research output has been significantly amplified, evidenced by 8 scientific publications and active participation in multiple high-profile international conferences, including SolarPACES

and CIES. Furthermore, the project successfully enhanced strategic engagement with stakeholders by organizing and completing four Regional Specialization Forums by Month 31, alongside making content from the Energy Strategy and Energy Transition Symposia widely available. Finally, concerning exploitation, an Innovation and Entrepreneurship assets Matrix is under development, complementing the training sessions already delivered in multiple Project Management (ProM) workshops. These integrated activities ensure robust dissemination, clear IP protection planning, and strong local integration, supported by the implemented Living Amenities content and Mentoring program.

Table 5. Summary of Progress towards Widening Impact 5 (WI.5): Research Dissemination and Exploitation.

WI.5: UEvora research reaches 4Helix actors, is protected, accessible and exploited		
Description	Pathway	Status
- UEvora RI and JRA are presented in peer-reviewed journals and Scientific Conferences	- Publication of articles in peer-reviewed Journals - Participation in SolarPACES and ISES International Conferences	- 8 Scientific Publications - Participation in SolarPACES'23, CIES24, SolarPACES'24, SolarPACES'25, and IWCB24.
- SALTOpower research impacts on Energy Transition and on the National and Regional Industrial and Specialization Strategies are clear to Academia, Policy and Industrial actors	- SALTOpower Energy Strategy Symposium - SALTOpower Energy Transition Symposium - SALTOpower Regional Specialisation Forum	- ESSymp contents available - ETSymp contents available - 4 RSForum took place by M31
- SALTOpower results exploitation encompasses a clear Intellectual Property Protection path and Commercial Exploitation Plan, embedded into a "Spin-off Blueprint"	- Spin-Off" blueprint"	- Innovation and Entrepreneurship contents and sessions already took place in ProMs #3, #4, #5, and #6; Innovation and Entrepreneurship assets Matrix defined and under development
- UEvora researchers and staff are fully integrated with the local actors and context	- Living Amenities Facility	- Living Amenities contents implemented in SALTOpower website; Mentoring Initiative implemented

3. RELATED PLANS (FOLLOWING PM² METHODOLOGY)

Deliverables Acceptance Plan

The management of the formal customer's acceptance of project deliverables (responsibilities, activities and the criteria for the deliverables acceptance) is described in the *Deliverables Acceptance Plan*. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

Project Description of Action

The *Project Description of Action* includes the project Work Plan and captures all types of resource requirements, schedule and effort/costs foreseen for the deliverables acceptance activities. The location of this artefact is found in Appendix 1.

APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

The Project documents will be stored in a shared drive located on the DLR server in Germany. The access will be granted by that partner, and each user will have a different access according to their profile, role and responsibility in the project.

The Project Steering Committee (PSC) will have access and editing permissions to all folders in the drive. The Project Core Team (PCT) will have editing access to respective WP folders and reading access to the remaining ones. The Project Support Team (PST) will have reading access to WP folders, and finally, the Project Owner (PO) may have reading access to all folders, including legal documents.

In each folder, the latest PDF and Word versions of each document will be available, and the previous versions shall be conserved in a separate folder named [versions] until the end of the project.

At the end of the project, each partner will make a copy of the shared folder to be stored in their own organisation's drive, and this must be kept following internal organisational procedures.

ID	Reference or <Related Document>	Source or <Link/Location>
1	Project folder	
2	Project Description of Action (Part A) <101079303_Annex 1 - Description of the action (part A).pdf>	Project folder
3	Project Description of Action (Part B) <101079303_Annex 1 - Description of the action (part B).pdf>	Project folder
4	D1.2 Data Management Plan <SALTOPOWER_D_1_2_DATA_MANAGEMENT_PLAN_05-05-2023_v_2>	Project folder
5	D1.3 Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan <SALTOPOWER_D_1_3_DEC_PLAN_13-09-2023_v_2>	Project folder
6	D4.1 Regional, National and International Fora Report <SALTOPOWER_D_4_1_Regional, National and International Fora Report_23-06-2025_v_1>	Project folder
7	Deliverables acceptance Checklist <[29.I.PM2.v3].Deliverables_Acceptance_Checklist.SALTOPOWER.10-02-2023.v1.0>	Project Folder
8	Deliverables Acceptance Plan <[08.I.PM2.v3].Deliverables_Acceptance_Plan.SALTOPOWER.14-02-2023.v.1>	Project Folder